

сыграть свою определённую роль. Она отмечала необычайную широту цветаевских аллюзий и многовариантность смыслов авторских текстов, а также их пространственную открытость. Английских критиков также восхищала предельная исповедальность цветаевского текста, не свойственная английской культурной традиции. Они отмечали индивидуальную способность М. Цветаевой выйти за рамки камерных и личных тем и достичь того, чтобы социально – политическая тематика зазвучала очень лично.

Список источников

1. Элиот Т.С. Традиция и индивидуальный талант назначение поэзии.- М.,2008.-194 с.
2. Вейдле В. «Эмбриология поэзии».Париж,-1980,-308с.

3. Бродский И. предисловие, поэт и проза:/ Марина Цветаева. избранная проза в двух томах. 1917-1937-т1. У IV. У.-1979,-т.1- W.Y.-1979.

4. Бройтман С.Н. Историческая поэтика. М.,2001-301с.

5. Livingstone A. Marina Tsvetaeva and Russian Poetry// Melbourne Slavonic studies.-1971.- P. 109-120

6. Mirsky D. A Russian letter: Recent Developments in poetry: Poetry and politics // the Londov Mercury.- 1921.- T.IV .-19 p.

7. Karlinsky S. Marina Tsvetaeva/ The woman.. her word and her poetry. Cambridge.1985

8. Schweitzer Y. Tsvetaeva.-IV.- Y.-1992

9. Mc.Duff Note on translatory Tsvetaeva// Marina Tsvetaeva . Selected Poems. Newcastle- upon- Tyne, 1998.-107 p.

METAPHOR AND METONYMY IN A COMPARATIVE ASPECT

Mammadzada S.

*Doctor of philosophy
Odlar Yurdu University*

Abstract

According to the cognitive theory that has developed in modern linguistics, the processes of metaphorization and metonymization are based on the processing of knowledge structures fixed in the human cognitive system in the form of various concepts and frames. In this article we will try to solve those main problems, which, first of all, include metaphor and metonymy as the two main types of semantic changes, as a ready-made metaphorical and metonymic meaning, metaphorization and metonymization as the main method and means of objectifying linguistic images of the surrounding reality. Despite the long history of the study of metonymy and metaphor in linguistics, certain issues of linguistic phenomena continue to cause controversy, since there is still no unambiguous assessment of their linguistic status in the language system. As a result of this, the research interest in epithet (figurative) vocabulary in modern linguistic research is still not weakening, on the contrary, it is only rapidly growing day by day. The interest of linguists in metonymy is also due to the relationship between the speaker's statement and the objective reality he is aware of, since connections by contiguity exist not between meanings, but in reality.

Keywords: metaphor, metonymy, discourse, cognitive linguistics, interpretation.

Introduction

In linguistic research, a special interest in the study of metaphor and metonymy in the second half of the last century is due, first of all, to a change in the scientific paradigm of research, the so-called "cognitive revolution". It should be noted here that any new scientific paradigm takes and appropriates a lot from the previous paradigm, whether by attraction or, conversely, by repulsion. Deeply realizing that a purely linguistic approach to the solution of linguistic facts and phenomena is not always self-sufficient, scientists turned to a paradigm that combines cognitive, discursive and pragmatic characteristics structural language units. In other words, in the context of modern scientific paradigms, especially within the anthropocentric paradigm, researchers consider language not in itself, but in relation to what people do. From the right point of all linguistic research carried out in the discursive-communicative perspective, is "human and language". An important point is the fact that the cognitive theory of language illuminates linguistic phenomena from three main as-

pects at once - representative, semiotic and interpretative. It is precisely to the cognitive approach to the study of the structural units of the language that opens up new horizons and opportunities for scientists in linguistic research. Only the cognitive paradigm, formed on the basis of anthropocentrism, in the center of which is a person with all his mental components, forms of social existence and cultural and creative activity and proceeding from the position that language activity is one of the aspects of the general cognitive activity of a person, helps to deepen and expand knowledge about the language. The study of the cognitive mechanisms of the conceptualization of the surrounding world, reflected in the linguistic picture of the world, contributes to the penetration into the human linguistic consciousness and is the most effective way to study the active interaction of language and thinking. Thus, natural language gradually turned into an object of ideological criticism due to the fact that it has now become regarded by linguists as the main tool for manipulating consciousness and normalizing the social behavior of people in society.

Methodology.

Research methods of article are predetermined by the purpose of this work and the specific tasks set in it. This work uses a complex methodology for the analysis of linguistic material, which includes a descriptive-analytical method, methods of interpretation, field, frame, functional analysis, and also a simulation method.

The main provisions put forward for defense:

- metonymy is a two-dimensional functional language phenomenon. It, as a way of forming and accumulating knowledge, is a cognitive-discursive activity of a linguo-creative subject and is a cognitive process of metonymic education, which consists in transferring the focus of attention during conceptualization of a certain extralinguistic reality;

- metonymy as a two-faced phenomenon is a process of verbalization of the results of cognition with the help of units of secondary nomination;

- metonymization is carried out within the framework of a certain metonymic model and is an ordered cognitive representation of a fragment of extralinguistic reality;

- metonymization is a mental process, within the framework of which one "concept-means" creates cognitive access to another "concept-goal" within a single conceptual system. Within the framework of discourse, it realizes its cognitive, pragmatic and discourse-forming functions.

Main part.

Metaphors and metonymies turned out to be a very convenient and at the same time mysterious object of research in the field of cognitive linguistics due to their special status, proximity to the sphere of human thought and consciousness. Both metaphor and metonymy are not just a part of natural language, but they directly reflect the specific features of human thinking. In addition, the blurring of the boundaries between individual conceptual areas often leads to the interaction of metaphor and metonymy. The conceptual description and explanation of metaphor and metonymy within the framework of cognitive models is one of the productive ways of cognition outside the linguistic reality and thinking through specific linguistic manifestations.

When presenting the main provisions of the problem, it should be recalled that according to the available literature on metaphor and metonymy, these categories have not yet been clearly distinguished. As a logical result of the existing uncertainty in modern cognitive linguistics, there is a twofold approach to the relationship between metonymy and metaphor. If the supporters of the first approach consider metaphor as the conceptual basis of metonymy, then according to the views of the supporters of the second approach, metonymy is the conceptual basis of metaphor. Therefore, some scientists, including R.O. Jakobson, for the first time expressed the opinion that from a general semiotic position, metaphor and metonymy form the basis of meaning formation in any semiotic system and clearly stated the existence of "a certain continuum, the opposite poles of which in the process conceptual projection are metaphor and metonymy" [3, p. 111]. According to this author, the continuum reflects the gradual transition

from metonymy to metaphor, and also helps to establish a boundary between the two processes at different points in the conceptual transition zones.

The primary source of the cognitive approach to metonymy was the early psychological and logical directions, in which metonymy was traditionally understood as the transfer of the name of an object (or phenomenon) on the basis of associative connections by adjacency, which are based on spatial, temporal, causal logical relationships between objects of reality, subject to naming, or rather renaming. In the linguistic works of recent years, devoted to the study of questions of metonymy, there is an intensive expansion of these explanations. In linguistic studies of recent years, metonymy is mainly explained as the transfer of a name according to the most diverse, practically any relations that exist between two phenomena, for example, the replacement of a cause by an effect, concrete - abstract, ideal - material, etc. However, in all these constant explanations and a general condition for the implementation of a transfer that is understandable for the addresser is the reference of the designated objects to one situation or one conceptual space. At the same time, it is also necessary to take into account that in the traditional interpretation of metonymy, adjacency relations in all their diversity are located in objective reality, while cognitive science considers them at the level of conceptualization.

In the "Linguistic Encyclopedic Dictionary" (1990), the concept of metonymy is interpreted as "a trope or mechanism of speech, consisting in the regular or occasional transfer of a name from one class of objects or a single object to another class or a separate object, one situation. The basis of metonymy is the spatial, eventual and syntagmatic relations between various categories belonging to reality and its reflection in the human mind, fixed by the meanings of words - between objects, persons, actions, phenomena, social institutions and events, place, time, etc." [5, c. 300]. In the same linguistic dictionary, a metaphor is considered as "a trope or a mechanism of speech, consisting in the use of a word denoting a certain class of objects and phenomena, to designate or name an object that is part of another class of objects, similar to this in any respect." [5, p. 296].

Metonymic transfer cannot be regarded as a simple linguistic device that generates the semantic ambiguity of a linguistic sign. Rather, it is a fundamental cognitive mechanism inherent in the ordinary, practical human consciousness. Metonymic transfer is entirely based on the cognitive operation of profiling, which, of course, ultimately leads to the actualization of the leading features of the subject of thought. This cognitive operation, profiling as a visual manifestation of the properties of the source in the target area, causes the structuring of a certain conceptual area and the identification of an important component of an event or object from a cognitive point of view.

Metonymy is, on the one hand, a mechanism of cognition, which is based on two complementary cognitive operations - the interaction of the source sphere and the target sphere, on the other hand, linguistic signs of secondary nomination, as a material (verbalized)

manifestation of conceptual phenomena. The secondary nomination acts as a linguistic mechanism for the linguistic categorization of a person's social status and involves the implementation of a subjective-emotional assessment. For metonymy, compression (narrowing) is important and characteristic, where the primary nomination often turns out to be superfluous, and instead of it, a secondary, transformed nomination is usually used, which in real use has a more important semantic meaning. So, for example, in the correlations of the following expressions "medicine for the head" - a collapsed combination of "medicine for headache", "drink two glasses" - "drink water in volume two glasses" (drink two glasses of water), the first part of the correlation is more common than the second part. Metonymy, first of all, is result-oriented and, unlike metaphor, it is not interpreted, but only deciphered by the addresser (listener), since the direct and figurative form of the information explication form are semantically identical.

The conceptualization of extralinguistic reality is mainly metaphorical in nature, that is, a person's understanding of objects and phenomena is based on a re-thinking of the basic concepts of human experience. At the same time, both metonymy and metaphor are different types of processes, as J. Lakoff and M. Johnson note: "Metaphor is a way to think about one phenomenon through the prism of another and its primary function is understanding. However, metonymy, performing mainly the function of reference in the traditional interpretation and allowing the use of the name of one object instead of another, also provides understanding" [4, p. 36].

The primary basis for metonymic shifts in the conceptual system is the selectivity of human consciousness, which is reflected in the language in the form of different shifts in the focus of attention when describing the same extralinguistic situation. Based on these considerations, E.V. Paducheva in her study distinguishes three types of metonymic transfers: 1) conceptual metonymy; 2) dictionary metonymy; 3) syntactic metonymy. According to the author, with conceptual metonymy, "adjacency links exist not between meanings, but in reality. ...an example of conceptual metonymy is the containing-contents model. With dictionary metonymy, a metonymic shift connects two meanings of a word recorded in the dictionary - if one meaning is obtained from the other" [11, p. 242]. According to her arguments, "syntactic metonymy from a semantic point of view is the transfer of the focus of attention from one participant to another with the help of a syntactic construction" [11, p. 243].

The main conceptual essence of metaphorization is that it is entirely based on the interaction of two structures of knowledge - the source and the goal. The process of structuring some areas of the goal according to the model of the source in modern cognitive science is called a metaphorical projection or cognitive mapping of extralinguistic reality in units of the second nomination. In addition to metaphorical ways of perceiving and understanding extralinguistic reality, there are also metonymic methods based on the logical grounds for discovering a connection between the signifier and the

signified of the conceptual model. According to the definition of R.O. Jakobson, "metaphor and metonymy are the basis of meaning formation in any semiotic system" [3, p.129].

Since the basis of the processes of metaphorization and metonymization are the procedures for processing the structures of linguocultural knowledge, they, first of all, turn out to be cognitive phenomena that directly affect human thinking. In other words, the metaphor directly affects the decision-making process, i.e. metaphorical comprehension of extralinguistic reality contributes to the formation of an alternative to resolving a problem situation. As J. Lakoff and M. Johnson rightly emphasize, "metaphors are essentially phenomena that provide understanding" [6, p. 208].

Metonymy, like metaphor, is inextricably linked with the ability to think and should be considered as a sign operation, during which one sign (or object) gets the opportunity to act instead of another sign (or object). In other words, metaphor and metonymy are essentially two main types of deviations from the basic normative level. As a result of the expansion of the original meaning, the metaphor turns into metonymy. Metonymy, as well as metaphor, takes an active part in the process of conceptualization and categorization of linguoculturally significant knowledge. Metaphorical expressions reflect the way people think about the concepts and phenomena of the world, and even as a result of the use of metaphors and metonymy, the way a person thinks develops and strengthens. Metonymic re-thinking is the transfer of the names of phenomena, objects and their attributes according to their contiguity or their connection in space and time. Metonymy allows you to more accurately concentrate on certain aspects denoted by a given lexeme of concepts. Metaphorical mapping involves two conceptual areas, while metonymic mapping involves one. In our opinion, this fact is an important and the only significant difference between metonymy and metaphor.

Of course, metaphor as a cognitive structure permeates our entire everyday life, not only spoken language, but also thinking and practical activities, and it is necessary for comprehending special, or rather, objects, things and objects that are difficult for the mind to understand. Metaphorically, first of all, human thinking itself, and linguistic metaphors act as their external manifestation. In other words, the metaphorical process is deeply rooted in the very structure of natural language. She is not just an entity behind which one can see something. Metaphors are embedded in the conceptual system of a person and therefore they find a concrete expression in human language. It is known that associations coming from the source of the target by the contiguity of objects and phenomena within the same conceptual space will certainly lead to the process of metonymization. The process of metonymization, as a way of forming new lexical units and as the formation of a cognitive-semantic structure, is simpler and more natural for linguistic use and linguistic consciousness than metaphorization. However, looking ahead, we immediately note that this reality allows us to give the polar relationship between metaphor and metonymy a general functional meaning, reflecting the polarity of

the metaphorical and metonymic processes of human thinking.

Reflecting the conceptual essence of language, metonymy plays a special role in human cognitive activity and acts as a means and method of mastering extralinguistic reality, in the process of which a person comprehends and designates the surrounding realities and phenomena. Metonymy, along with metaphor, is the cultivation of living spaces and is the most important source of mental processes in the field of individual and social consciousness. It, as the most important source and form of mental processes, contributes to the formation of a representative sample, the description of the whole in parts, the identification of causal relationships between involved phenomena and objects. It, like a metaphor, actively operates in the cognitive processes of conceptualization and categorization of our knowledge. Metonymy allows a native speaker to conceptualize a perceived object through its relation to another object. Therefore, J. Lakoff and M. Johnson are quite right when they note that " *metonymic concepts structure not only language, but also thinking, relationships and actions* " [4, p. 37].

Metonymy can be attributed to semantic transfers due to the fact that changes in meaning occur on the basis of the interaction of different conceptual spheres. Metonymy is the result of a derived meaning and is directly involved in the enrichment and expansion of the human conceptual system and language inventory with the help of cognitive operations on already existing linguistic meanings. It is a universal and multifaceted linguistic phenomenon and it can, more precisely, be expediently studied in different planes. Metonymy is not a direct, but a figurative characteristic of a lexeme (word). Considering metonymy as a stylistic device that can form a new word, I.R. Galperin emphasized that " *metonymy is based on the relationship between lexical and contextual meanings, based on a certain association that connects the concepts expressed in these meanings of words* " [2, p. 144].

Now consider these listed postulates separately. Let's start with the concept of metonymy. It is not only the name of an object, but also contains an indication of the concept underlying the lexical meaning of the word. As an example, J. Lakoff and M. Johnson use the statement /She's just a pretty face/. In this English statement, according to the authors, we operate with the concepts "face" and "person" and use the conceptual model of metonymic relations "face instead of person". Based on this example, it can be argued that with metonymy one member of a category can replace the entire category [4, p. 79-90].

When considering metonymy as a cognitive process, it should be said that traditionally metonymy is understood as a process of substitution and this approach underlies the models of metonymic relations, word 1 instead of word 2. As proof, we can use the above example: /She is just a pretty face/. In this English sentence " *face* " is used instead of " *person* ", and the whole sentence is understood by us as /She is just a pretty person/. However, in our opinion, this provision does not fully correspond to reality, since the second sentence implies that a person is completely beautiful,

although the first statement emphasizes that only the "face" of a person is beautiful. An expression, on the other hand, would sound absurd: /She is a pretty person but does not have a pretty face/. These two types of metonymy: " the face for the person " and " the person for the face " are in relation to interaction, since the "face" of a person evokes in the addressee the image of the person himself, in other words, the person makes him think about his "face". This means that metonymy, as a cognitive process, does not simply replace one concept with another, but makes them interact and forms a new complex conceptual meaning at their intersection.

An important feature of metonymic models is the presence of a function that links one element of the model with another in the conceptual system. In a model that expresses the relationship between the part and the whole, there is a relationship between them that allows the part to replace the whole. In this case, it is necessary to approve the transfer of the name of one object to another according to their external adjacency. Here the concept of adjacency acts as a unifying link when considering metonymy between traditional and cognitive approaches. Adjacency from the position of conceptualization (cognition) exists within the framework of idealized cognitive models, and the basis of these models is the totality of our knowledge about the subject of reality. Being highly conventionalized units, metaphors are used to create figurative meanings and are represented by relationships between the meanings of one lexical unit. For example, the idealized cognitive model "Lesson" covers the following range of concepts: class, desk, chair, students, teacher, blackboard, homework, lesson, etc.

Based on the thoughts reflected in the above citations, it can be generalized that in modern cognitive studies, metonymy is considered mainly as a transfer, based mainly on the contiguity of phenomena and objects. In his concept, A.Barcelona diligently insists on the idea that " *all metaphors are motivated by metonymy, and in order to prove the correctness of his theory, he uses the following examples, in which the area - the source of the metaphorical concept is motivated by metonymy* " (Sadness is Down) [1, p. 31].

Speaking about metaphor and metonymy, it should be noted once again that in the special scientific literature there is no unique opinion on this issue. The main difference between cognitive metaphor and metonymy is that the interaction of two concepts within the framework of metonymy is carried out in the space of a single conceptual area.

The development of cognitive linguistics, on the one hand, greatly influenced the expansion of the interpretation of metonymy, on the other hand, it actively contributed to the separation of linguistic metonymy, as a semantic way of developing the meaning of a lexeme, from cognitive metonymy, as a method of conceptualization and categorization of extralinguistic reality. Within the framework of the already established cognitive linguistics, a fairly wide range of terminological apparatus has been created, which is successfully used in describing the cognitive mechanisms of metonymy.

From the point of view of cognitive science, metonymy is a basic characteristic of human thinking, not

only creative, but also everyday thinking. At the mental level, the human brain accumulates and processes information that comes into it from the outside world. During this process, a certain information structure is formed, reflecting the cognitive experience of a person in the form of different concepts. In this conceptual system, metonymy acts as a cognitive model (conceptual structure), between the components of which there is a substitution relation. In other words, metonymy is a figure of speech in which the name is transferred by quality, based on adjacency, on the connection between two objects in reality. Metonymy is based on the connection of things, phenomena and is the result of the designation of one thing through another, associated with it by contiguity. Such a two-layer conceptual structure is characterized by a substitution relation and is rightly called the metonymic model. The main essence of the cognitive mechanism of metonymy is that within the framework of the conceptual area, a certain concept (concept-means - *vehicle / trigger concept*) can represent its other concept (concept-target - *target concept*) or replace the entire area as a whole. In metonymization, the substitution of areas is due to the contiguity of the phenomena being comprehended in reality - the presence of some real connection between them (phenomena, objects). However, this does not mean at all that the metonymic transfer is a simple mental projection of one phenomenon onto another, which has an ontological connection with each other, but rather it involves a number of mental operations, namely the profiling of one or another element of the conceptualized area. In the conceptual system, the following metonymic oppositions are best known: "*part – whole, whole – part, material – object, producer – product, place – institution*" [7, p. 66].

Within the theory of cognitive semantics, the following main methods of metonymic transfers can be distinguished: a) "human over non-human" (here, the human is priority over inanimate entities); b) "concrete over abstract" (here the concrete is expressed in relation to the abstract); c) bodily entities are used to denote actions, for example, "hold your tongue" instead of "stop speaking"; d) bodily entities are used to denote emotions, for example, "he is heartless"; e) bodily organs are used to express perceptual processes, for example, "lend me your ear".

Metonymy is used to represent different personal identities. For example, a person refers himself to a certain group and considers himself as part of something larger (family, team, people). For example: /I also want to live dangerously and get brown. I want to see my doughy English skin change from white sliced to wheat germ// (Townsend). In this segment of the text, a person speaks not just about pale skin, but about "pale English skin" and, with the help of metonymic transfer, indicates his national identity. Metonymy can be used in utterances to represent some feature of a body part, for example, the hands of an artist, the posture of a ballerina, the soul of a poet, etc.

Metonymy and metaphor are mainly united by their direct participation in the processes of human cognitive activity. They are directly related to thinking and have a direct impact on the perception of extralinguistic

reality. The main immanent property that distinguishes metaphor, metonymy and other rhetorical figures from other linguistic means is that they are able to represent both universal and cultural concepts. The concept of idealized cognitive models, as an ordered cognitive representation of a fragment of objective reality, was further developed in the studies of Z. Kovechek. Considering the role of metonymy in the cognition and representation of linguocultural knowledge about the world, the author in his study exposes it as a "*cognitive process, where the content area of the concept-means provides mental access to the content area of the concept-goal within the same domain, or idealized cognitive models*" [12, p. 19]. However, the greatest research interest among scientists is the question of similarities and differences between them. According to Z. Kovechek, "*a conceptual metaphor is the unity of two conceptual areas that are far from each other, based on similarity in some way. Metonymy is more characterized by adjacency relations that arise between elements of the same conceptual area, or an idealized cognitive model (idealized cognitive model)*" [5, p. 160].

From the point of view of formal logic, language laws are violated in metaphors and metonyms, since contradictory concepts are combined with each other, opposites are identified, small concepts are replaced by large ones, or vice versa. Sometimes the grammatical laws of a certain language are violated in specific implementations, for example, native speakers often use the plural instead of the singular, the present tense instead of the past, etc. However, violation and deviation from the grammatical laws of the language is permissible only in certain situations. Thus, metaphor and metonymy in a certain context are understood as a mechanism for replacing signs associated with cultural frames.

Metonymy and metaphor, as a means of understanding the forms of knowledge representation, serve as models in accordance with which a person thinks and acts in the act of communication. When distinguishing metaphor from metonymy, scientists mainly proceed from the position according to which metonymy reflects, by contiguity, the objectively existing state of things in reality. As for the metaphor, it creates mental entities that have no analogues in external reality, as if imposing its own vision of the surrounding reality. They are figures of speech, special types of occasional nomination, more precisely, repeated nomination. Being conditional phenomena, they represent the formation of figurative meanings and, thus, are relations between the meanings of one lexical unit. However, there are certain semantic, syntactic and functional differences between them. Unlike metonymy, metaphor is a semantic operation, while metonymy is a syntactic operation. First, metaphorization is directly related to the transfer of only some features of the source area to the target area, highlighting them in the target area and characterizing it (target area) based on these features. Of course, among the rhetorical means of the language, the most common and commonly used are metaphors and metonymy. The first of them acts as one of the figurative means of representing reality. For example:

/Along with the idea of romantic love, she was introduced to another - *physical beauty*. Probably the most destructive idea in the history of human thought// (Along with the idea of romantic love, she was introduced to another - physical beauty . Probably the most destructive idea in the history of human thought) [10, c . 122].

In this segment, the author emphasizes the insignificance of physical beauty . With the help of a metaphor, the author was able to describe in reality how much trouble "beauty" can bring. In addition, the "beauty" of white people deals a heavy blow to the psychology of black people, greatly hinders the development of their sense of self-confidence. For example :

/I even think now that the land of the entire country was hostile to marigolds that year. This soil is bad for certain kinds of flowers. Certain seeds it will not nurture , certain fruits it will not bear, and the land kills of its own volition, we acquiesce and say the victim had no right to live // it will not grow seeds, it will not bear certain fruits, and the earth kills of its own accord, we agree and say that the victim had no right to life) [10, p . 206].

The metaphorical relationship between meanings is characterized as based on the similarity of the designated phenomena and objects. The semantic connection within the conceptual area that forms the metaphorical model is much stronger than outside. For example, the phrases "flame tongue", "bell tongue", and "tongue in a man's mouth" are similar in form. In other words, in a conceptual system, a metaphorical model acts as a conceptual area (source area), the elements of which are connected by various semantic relations (perform a function, contribute, be a part, etc.), and each element of the model is connected to other elements by stronger links, than with elements of other conceptual domains.

With metonymization, a holistic projection of the concept-source onto the concept-target takes place, i.e. the first area crushes the second under itself, taking over its referential function. First, traditionally metonymic relations between meanings are based on the contiguity of the phenomena and objects denoted . For example, in the modern sense, "work" means not only a certain type of activity, but also the place where this activity is performed. Secondly, if the metaphor goes beyond the syntagma , then metonymy, as a rule, remains within the framework of one syntagma. The expression of metonymy, as a rule, contains the designations of both interacting units and is limited to one syntagma, in contrast to the metaphor, which usually goes beyond its limits. For example , /The kettle is boiling// = /The water in the kettle is boiling//. /He was just seeing something with rage// = /He was excited to the point that it was like a boil //

In cognitive linguistics, metaphor and metonymy are often, in our opinion, justifiably called a secondary nomination, which has an associative character and allows you to create nominations based on the similarity (metaphor) or contiguity (metonymy) of language units. Metonymy, as well as metaphor , are the most productive ways of forming new nominative units in any natural languages, since the language experiences a constant "fierce hunger" in the designation of new

concepts. The main difference between these phenomena is that a metaphor is a process of predication of a property obtained on the basis of analogy, resulting in a simplification of the semantic structure of the word, while with metonymy the semantic field expands due to the introduction of a new component in the meaning of reality. Metonymy, in the definition of Yu.M. Lotman, is designated as the process of " *singling out the essential-specific and eliminating the inessential* " [8, p.149].

From the point of view of the cognitive approach, metonymy is one of the methods for the formation of knowledge about extralinguistic reality in the form of special cognitive units. Metonymy, as a rule, contains explicit references to physical or causal associations between phenomena or objects. On the basis of the analyzes carried out, it can be argued that the foundations of metonymic concepts are more obvious, since metonymic relations, as J. Lakoff emphasizes, " *are rooted in our experience* " [7, p. 66].

In general, metonymy can be considered as a cognitive mechanism for the representation of linguoculturally significant knowledge. The main essence of metonymic transfer lies in the fact that a certain area of conceptual content serves as a means of representing the whole concept. Within the framework of a conceptual structure, one of the concepts included in it can represent another, related concept or the entire structure as a whole. Metonymy, as a cognitive process, implements the imposition within one model, one category within one model replaces another. The activation of one cognitive category, connecting it with another within one conceptual system, is the main function of metonymic expression. For example :

*/We need a couple of strong bodies for our team //
/ There are a lot of good hands in the workshop //
/We need some new faces around here //*

It is clear that in the above examples we are talking about people, but in each sentence a certain quality of a person is indicated. If in the sports context of the 1st example the "physical strength" model associated with the category "body" is explained, then in the 2nd sentence, i.e. in the context of art, the author highlights the "skills" model associated with the "hand" category, and finally, in the third option, it is indicated that the "face" category is especially necessary in the context of acquaintance, because it is the face of a person that we usually perceive when meeting strangers.

A review of the literature on the topic under study clearly shows that there is disagreement among scientists when defining metonymy. Different scientists give different definitions to this very mysterious linguistic phenomenon. Some linguists define metonymy as a transformation or transfer of a name based on the adjacencies of concepts, while others, for example, I.P. Galperin interprets metonymy as a phenomenon that " *replaces one name of an object with another based on the connection that exists between these objects* " [2, p.130].

If we consider that metonymy is a linguistic phenomenon based on the causal relationship of a word,

then we can safely say that one of the important functions of metonymy is the transfer of the name of one object or phenomenon to another. For example :

/ The final years before his stroke, his old-fashioned spectacles, bushy eyebrows, and deeply lined face made him look more like a retired college professor than the *blue-collar* he had been// [14, p. 6]. (*In the last years before he had a stroke, his old-fashioned glasses, thick eyebrows, and wrinkled face gave him the appearance of a retired college teacher, it was by no means possible to say that in the past this man belonged to a detachment of factory workers in blue coats*).

In the English version of this sentence, "blue-collar" is an alias for workers in a factory, who usually wear blue and white overalls.

Metonymy has a complex structure, on the one hand, it is a purely symbolic element, on the other hand, it is an element of the symbolic construction of expressive meaning, contiguity. It, as an expressive means of language, is aimed at creating a certain effect of persuasion, emotional reaction and special evidence.

Based on a review of modern literature on the topic under study, it can be unequivocally stated that at this stage of development, cognitive linguistics does not have a clearly formulated definition of metonymy as a cognitive process. Due to the lack of clear boundaries between metaphor and metonymy, it is assumed that there are intermediate zones that allow, for example, the formation of a metaphor due to metonymy, for example, "*high prices*" [13, p. 417]. However, despite the lack of clear boundaries between metaphor and metonymy in linguistics, it is worth noting that metonymy, as the root cause of metaphorization, motivating metaphor, is recognized by a number of cognitive scientists.

Findings.

It is known that verbal art is a universal manifestation of culture, and therefore, in the construction of discourse, the aesthetic function comes to the fore, which implies a conscious attitude to the design of live speech. The metaphorical use of language is based on comparison, and the combination of linguistic units is based on metonymic use, which is based on the contiguity of phenomena and objects of the world. If we take into account that metaphorical relations correlate with paradigmatics, and metonymic relations with syntagmatics, then the former should be considered at the level of the language system, and the latter at the level of implementation. In this situation, the key point of difference is the reference: if the metaphor causes the transfer of meaning, then metonymy causes the transfer of reference and the use of ellipsis, since metonymic relations are established between objects and do not depend on the language used to express these relations. This means that natural language acts not only as a means of communication and expression, but also as an object of representation. Metonymy, as a creative way of understanding conceptual abstractions and formulating new thoughts, plays one of the leading roles in the processes of structuring human consciousness. Metonymy, as a mental phenomenon, is one of the main characteristics of human cognition. The main differences between these processes are that a metaphor is a way of describing one thing in terms of another, and its leading

function is to provide comprehension and understanding of reality. Metonymy performs mainly the function of reference, allowing one entity to replace another within a single domain. Metaphor, on the other hand, gives a description of the object, it performs a characterizing function. Metonymy looks at the individualizing quality, allowing the addressee of speech to identify the object - the function of identification, to highlight the object, to distinguish it from other objects, for example, to identify the whole by its characteristic part. Metonymic transformations, which are based on the principle of adjacency, are mental operations on one frame. The phenomenon of metonymization is inherent in semantic one-dimensionality, therefore, unlike metaphorization, its figurative effectiveness is much weaker and not noticeable.

Thus, it is not always possible to draw a clear line between metaphor and metonymy, and this is explained by a number of common features. Both metaphor and metonymy are conceptual in nature, which is expressed in the regularity of transfers, both of them can be conventional, and can be a model of human thinking, both are a means of enriching and expanding the arsenal of language units can be explained as a process of representation. Metonymy exists outside the framework of language, contributing to the structuring of human thinking and activity. As a cognitive mechanism, it provides an opportunity to perceive one phenomenon of extralinguistic reality within the framework of its connections with other phenomena of the world.

So, in this article, we understand conceptual metonymy as a cognitive model, which is the interaction of cognitive metaphor and cognitive metonymy. In our opinion, metonymy is one of the ways of semantic shifts within the lexeme and is the key to understanding and interpreting the processes of human thinking. Being a language model, it is a mental reflection of a fragment of reality in the form of relationships between the whole and its parts. In our work, we perceive metonymy as a cognitive process, as a mental operation that forms new concepts, without which the conceptualization and categorization of the reality surrounding us and human existence is impossible. Being an important tool in the conceptualization of categories, it is one of the effective language mechanisms for organizing the language picture of the world, since as the concepts become more complex, the mechanisms of verbalization of the surrounding reality become more complicated.

References

1. Barcelona, A. On the plausibility of claiming a metonymic motivation for conceptual metaphor // *Metaphor and Metonymy at the Crossroads: A Cognitive Perspective* / ed. by A. Barcelona. Berlin - N.Y.: Mouton de Gruyter, 2003. - p. 31-58.
2. Galperin, I.R. *Essays on the style of the English language* / I.R. Galperine. - Moscow: Publishing house of literature in foreign languages, - 1958. - 459 p.
3. Jacobson, R.O. *Two Aspects of Language and Two Types of Aphatic Violations* // *Theory of Metaphor: Sat. : per. from English, French, German, Spanish, Polish. lang.* / [intro. Art. and comp. N.D.

Arutyunova; total ed. N. D. Arutyunova and M. A. Zhurinskaya]. - M.: Progress, -1990. -With. 110-132.

4. Landtsheer, C.de. Introduction to the Study of Political Discourse. Politically Speaking: A Worldwide Examination of Language Used in the Public Sphere. Eds. O. Feldman, C. De Landtsheer. London and Westport, Conn., Praeger, 1998.a, pp. 1-16.

5. Langacker, R.W. Reference-Point Constructions // Cognitive linguistics, 4 / R.W. Langacker. - 1993. - pp. 29-40.

6. Lakoff, J. Women, fire and dangerous things: what categories of language tell us about thinking / J. Lakoff. - Moscow: Languages of Slavic Culture, - 2004. - 791 p.

7. Lakoff, J. Metaphors we live by / Lakoff J., M. Johnson. - Moscow: URSS Editorial, -2008. - 256p.

8. Lotman, Yu.M. Selected articles / Articles on semiotics / T.I, Part II. -Moscow, -1962. - With. 144-154.

9. Linguistic encyclopedic dictionary / Ch. ed. V. N. Yartseva. - Moscow: Soviet Encyclopedia, 1990. - 685 p

10. Newsweek, Feb. 11, 2002, 25. https://www.forbes.com/2002/02/11/0211_facesam2.html

11. Paducheva, E. V. Space in the guise of time and vice versa (to the typology of metonymic transfers) / E. V. Paducheva // Logical analysis of the language. Languages of spaces / otv. ed. N. D. Arutyunova, I. B. Levontina. -M.: Languages of Russian culture, 2000. - p. 239-254.

12. Riemer, N. Remetonymizing metaphor: Hypercategories in semantic extension/ N.Reimer. Cognitive linguistics. 2002. - V. 12. - №4. - p. 379-401.

13. Scollon, R. Mediated Discourse as Social Interaction / R. Scollon - London: Routledge, 1998. - 330p

14. The Best of True Confessions. - N-Y, Spring 2005. No. 84. - 104 p